

Evaluation Of Proximate Composition, Lycopene Content, Betacarotene Content And DNA Quality Profiling In Tomato Varieties, *Lycopersicon Esculentum* (Mill.)

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18237866>

Abstract

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) is a nutritionally important vegetable widely cultivated in Nigeria. This study evaluated nineteen tomato varieties for proximate composition, antioxidant content (lycopene and β -carotene), and DNA quality to provide a comprehensive assessment of their nutritional and molecular attributes. The nineteen tomato varieties were obtained from the tomato germplasm collection of the National Center for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NACGRABB), Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. Standard methods were used for proximate, lycopene and β -carotene analysis while DNA quality was assessed using UV spectrophotometry and agarose gel electrophoresis. Moisture content ranged from 74.69 - 90.66%, Ash content from 1.99-5.36%, Fat content from 0.74 -3.86%, Crude Fiber from 0.74 -5.62%, Crude Protein from 2.59 - 7.06% and Carbohydrate from 0.85 - 7.70%. The lycopene content ranged from 3.020mg/100g to 31.629mg/100g while the β -carotene content ranged from 8.566 to 45.276mg/100g. The DNA quality ratios ranged between 1.457 and 2.000. Varieties: NGB02691, NGB02695, NGB05075, NGB00697, and NGB00707 were outstanding in terms of moisture content implying a prolonged period of storage; NGB02691, NGB02695, NGB00697, NGB00707 and Platinum 701F1 were outstanding in terms of β -carotene content while NGB00749, NGB00746 and Diva F1 were outstanding in terms of lycopene content. These tomato varieties with lower level of moisture content, high level of β -carotene and lycopene content can be improved upon through hybridization in tomato breeding programmes. Regular consumption of tomatoes in whatever form should be encouraged due to their antioxidant properties and as a major precursor of provitamin A, which is a vital for improved eye health.

Keywords: Proximate, Beta carotene, Lycopene, DNA , Tomato, varieties

INTRODUCTION

Tomato, *Lycopersicon esculentum* (Mill.) is a member of the family, Solanaceae (Mallick, 2021). In Nigeria, tomato plays a crucial role in household nutrition, providing essential nutrients such as vitamins A and C, minerals, and dietary fiber (Oyelakin *et al.*, 2022). It serves as a major source of essential micronutrients and bioactive compounds such as lycopene and beta-carotene,

which have been linked to the prevention and management of various chronic diseases, including cardiovascular disorders, cancers, and oxidative stress-related conditions (Tufail *et al.*, 2024). In addition to its health-promoting phytochemicals, tomatoes provide considerable quantities of dietary fiber, proteins, carbohydrates, ash, and lipids, contributing significantly to daily nutritional intake (Adedeji *et al.*, 2020). Isolation of high-quality genomic DNA is a crucial step in modern biological techniques such as DNA fingerprinting, genome mapping, PCR etc (Krawczak and Schmidtke, 2020). In addition, DNA quality assessment is vital for genomic studies, aiding in the identification, conservation, and genetic improvement of crop species (Nadeem *et al.*, 2018). Existing studies have mostly focused on individual parameters such as proximate composition (Akanbi *et al.*, 2012) or molecular characterization using DNA markers (Ogundele *et al.*, 2020), with few integrating both nutritional and genetic profiling in a single study. The need to characterize these varieties holistically is especially relevant in the face of increasing climate variability, rising food insecurity, and the push for functional foods with health-promoting properties (Wani *et al.*, 2023). The present study seeks to bridge this critical knowledge gap by providing a comprehensive evaluation of proximate composition, lycopene and beta-carotene content, and DNA quality in selected tomato varieties. The outcomes of this research will have significant implications for tomato breeding, food security, and global nutrition and to also serve as a reference for food scientists, geneticists and plant breeders so as to enhance decision making in tomato varieties recommendation and national food security strategies. This research is therefore embarked on to: (i) determine the proximate analysis of the tomato varieties, (ii) determine the β -carotene and lycopene content of the tomato and; (iii) determine the DNA quality of the tomato varieties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experimental materials for this project consist of twelve tomato genotypes, *Lycopersicon esculentum* (Mill.). The tomato varieties were obtained from the tomato germplasm collection of the National Center for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NACGRAB), Department of Plant Genetic Resources, Ibadan, Oyo – State, Nigeria. The names of the tomato, *Lycopersicon esculentum*(Mill.)varieties are; NGB02688, NGB02691, NGB02695, NGB05075, NGB05076, NGB05077, NGB00694, NGB00696, NGB00697, NGB00707, NGB00710, NGB00716, NGB00718, NGB00725, NGB00743, NGB00746, NGB00749, DivaF1 and Platinum701F1.

Proximate Analysis

Moisture, ash, crude protein, crude fat, crude fiber, and carbohydrate contents were determined using AOAC (2005) standard methods. Moisture was determined by oven-drying at 105°C, ash by muffle furnace incineration at 550°C, protein using the Kjeldahl method, fat by Soxhlet extraction, and fiber by acid and alkaline digestion. Carbohydrate content was calculated by difference.

Determination Of Lycopene And Beta-Carotene

Lycopene and beta-carotene were extracted using hexane-acetone-ethanol (2:1:1) solution, vortexed, filtered, and read using UV-Vis spectrophotometer at 503 nm and 450 nm, respectively.

Results were calculated using standard calibration curves and expressed in mg/100g fresh weight (Rotino *et al.*, 2005).

Dna Extraction And Quality Assessment

Fresh leaf tissues were used for DNA extraction following the Cetyltrimethylammonium Bromide (CTAB) protocol. DNA concentration and purity were measured using a NanoDrop spectrophotometer at 260 and 280 nm. Integrity was confirmed via 1% agarose gels (Aboul-Maaty and Oraby, 2019).

RESULTS

The estimates of the proximate composition of the tomato varieties are presented in Table 1. The moisture content of the tomato varieties ranged between 74.69 and 90.660%. The highest moisture content was recorded in V24 (90.660%) followed by V22 (90.380%), whereas the lowest level was recorded in V4 (74.690%). The ash content ranged from 1.99 to 5.36%. The highest ash content was recorded in V4 (5.36%) followed by V6 (5.33%), whereas the lowest was recorded in V24 (1.99%). As regards crude fat content, the highest level was recorded in V1 (3.860%), whereas the lowest was recorded in V22 (0.59%). The crude protein content was maximum in V26 (7.26%), whereas it was minimum in V24 (2.54%). The crude fibre content ranged between 0.47 and 5.62%. The highest level of crude fibre was recorded in V5 (5.62%) followed by V4 (5.40%) followed by V16 (4.04%), whereas it was lowest in V6 (0.47%). The carbohydrate content ranged from 0.85 to 7.70%. The highest level of carbohydrate was recorded in V10 (7.70%) followed by V4 (7.68%) followed by V9 (6.93%), whereas it was lowest in V5 (0.85%).

The estimates of the β -carotene and lycopene composition of the tomato varieties are presented in Table 2. The β -carotene content varied between 8.566 and 45.276mg/g, whereas the lycopene content ranged between 3.02 and 31.629mg/g. The highest β -carotene concentration was recorded in V3 (45.27mg/g) indicating potential for provitamin A contribution followed by V9 (39.778mg/g) followed by V10 (39.198mg/g) whereas the lowest concentration was recorded in V1 (8.566mg/g). The lycopene content likewise varied between 3.20 and 31.629mg/g. The highest lycopene was recorded in V26 (31.629mg/g) implying the fruits nutraceutical value and red colouration followed by V24 (30.500mg/g) followed by V23 (29.513mg/g), whereas the lowest concentration was recorded in V6 (3.02mg/g).

The estimates of the DNA quality of the tomato varieties using the CTAB protocol is presented in Table 3. The DNA quality ranged between 1.457 to 2.000. fifteen out of the nineteen tomato varieties recorded DNA quality within the acceptable range out of which only ten recorded the ideal DNA quality required for downstream application processes of 1.8 to 2.0 V3, V5, V7, V18 and V23 recorded DNA quality of 1.780, 1.758, 1.759, 1.798 and 1.750 respectively which required further purification before being used for PCR or gene sequencing. V2, V9, V10 and V14 with quality of 1.688, 1.678, 1.650 and 1.457 respectively, were highly contaminated with protein or phenol residue which makes them unsuitable for further downstream processes.

Table 1. Proximate Composition (%) of the Tomato Varieties

VAR. NO	MOISTURE CONTENT (%)	ASH (%)	FAT (%)	CRUDE FIBRE (%)	CRUDE PROTEIN (%)	CARBOHYDRATE (%)
V1	81.790a	4.050ab	3.860a	1.420bc	3.090b	5.790ab
V2	79.440ab	5.250a	3.770a	3.340ab	3.360b	4.840ab
V3	78.100ab	3.360	2.060ab	3.900ab	7.060a	5.520ab
V4	74.690ab	5.360a	3.480a	5.400a	3.390b	7.680a
V5	81.350a	4.030ab	1.510b	5.620a	6.640a	0.850cd
V6	81.470a	5.330a	3.720a	0.470c	4.280ab	4.730ab
V7	82.220a	3.230ab	1.800b	3.010ab	5.490a	4.250b
V8	82.430a	3.350ab	2.790a	3.830ab	3.950b	3.650b
V9	79.060ab	5.030a	2.660a	1.900	4.420ab	6.930a
V10	78.330ab	4.110ab	2.740a	3.360ab	3.760b	7.700a
V11	84.240a	3.32ab0	2.250ab	2.810ab	5.530a	1.850c
V14	82.600a	4.290ab	1.720b	2.030b	4.400ab	4.960ab
V16	83.220a	3.150ab	1.680b	4.040a	4.870ab	3.040b
V18	84.270a	3.130ab	2.720a	2.790ab	4.260ab	2.830bc
V22	90.380a	2.130b	0.590c	0.970c	4.140ab	1.790c
V23	90.430a	2.070b	0.740c	0.740c	4.030ab	1.990c
V24	90.660a	1.990bc	0.790c	1.020bc	2.590bc	2.950bc
V26	80.780ab	3.070ab	1.750b	2.940ab	7.260a	4.200b
V27	80.580ab	3.090ab	2.770a	2.900ab	4.900ab	5.760ab

Footnote: V1 =NGB02688; V2=NGB02691; V3=NGB02695; V4=NGB05075; V5=NGB05076 V6=NGB05077; V7=NGB00694; V8=NGB00696; V9=NGB00697; V10=NGB00707; V11=NGB00710; V14=NGB00716; V16=NGB00718; V18NGB00725; V22=NGB00743; V23=NGB00746; V24=NGB00749; V26=Divi F1; V27=Platinum701 F1.

Table 2: Estimates of Beta-Carotene and Lycopene composition of the Tomato Varieties

VAR. NO	BETA CAROTENE (mg/100g)	LYCOPENE (mg/100g)
1	8.566bc	15.797ab
2	35.399a	3.95c

3	45.276a	5.843bc
4	16.844ab	4.69bc
5	17.781ab	21.436a
6	15.958ab	3.02c
7	34.079a	4.37bc
8	31.265a	5.735bc
9	39.778a	9.188b
10	39.198a	11.122ab
11	15.469ab	24.696a
14	12.196b	7.821b
16	31.358a	7.49b
18	15.496ab	28.445a
22	14.343ab	27.075a
23	17.765ab	29.513a
24	15.233ab	30.5a
26	18.517ab	31.629a
27	35.293a	9.807b

Footnote: V1 =NGB02688; V2=NGB02691; V3=NGB02695; V4=NGB05075; V5=NGB05076 V6=NGB05077; V7=NGB00694; V8=NGB00696; V9=NGB00697; V10=NGB00707; V11=NGB00710; V14=NGB00716; V16=NGB00718; V18NGB00725; V22=NGB00743; V23=NGB00746; V24=NGB00749; V26=Divaf1; V27=Platinum701 F1.

Table 3: DNA Quality in Tomato varieties at A260/A280 using CTAB Protocol

VAR No	A260nm	A280nm	A260/A280
V1	0.686	0.371	1.850a
V2	0.235	0.139	1.688ab
V3	0.488	0.274	1.780a
V4	0.600	0.315	1.903a
V5	0.130	0.074	1.758a
V6	0.350	0.181	1.930a
V7	0.809	0.460	1.759a
V8	0.502	0.251	2.000a

V9	0.745	0.444	1.678ab
V10	0.332	0.201	1.650ab
V11	0.230	0.124	1.864a
V14	0.513	0.352	1.457b
V16	0.552	0.276	2.000a
V18	0.726	0.404	1.798a
V22	0.694	0.375	1.850a
V23	0.627	0.358	1.750a
V24	0.515	0.271	1.897a
V26	0.740	0.401	1.845a
V27	0.588	0.299	1.967a

Footnote: V1 =NGB02688; V2=NGB02691; V3=NGB02695; V4=NGB05075; V5=NGB05076 V6=NGB05077; V7=NGB00694; V8=NGB00696; V9=NGB00697; V10=NGB00707; V11=NGB00710; V14=NGB00716; V16=NGB00718; V18NGB00725; V22=NGB00743; V23=NGB00746; V24=NGB00749; V26=Divi F1; V27=Platinum701 F1.

DISCUSSION

The proximate composition analysis of the tomato varieties in this study revealed significant variation, among the varieties. The moisture content ranged from 74.69 % to 90.66 %. this is consistent with the findings of Sanusi et al. (2021), who also reported moisture content of 90.20–95.20 % in tomato. Varieties with lower moisture content, are likely to have longer shelf life and reduced susceptibility to microbial spoilage, making them suitable for processing and storage. The ash content, which ranged from 1.99 % to 5.36 %, indicates the mineral composition of the tomato fruits. This aligns with Adedeji et al. (2020), who emphasized the role of tomato as a source of micronutrients. Varieties with higher ash content may provide greater dietary mineral contributions, essential for human nutrition. The varying levels of crude fibre content recorded in this study corroborates the findings of Ali et al. (2022). High-fibre content in tomato is particularly beneficial for gastrointestinal health and may aid in the management of metabolic disorders. The carbohydrate content reported in this study, is similar to that of Abubakar and Musa (2020). The relatively low carbohydrate levels across most varieties indicate that tomato is a low-calorie food suitable for inclusion in diet plans. The varying levels of beta-carotene and lycopene concentrations in the tomato varieties indicated that they are important sources of antioxidants and provitamin A. The β -carotene content varied considerably from 8.566 mg/100 g to 45.276 mg/100 g. Varieties with high β -carotene, could serve as valuable sources of provitamin A, which is essential for vision, immune function, and prevention of vitamin A deficiency-related disorders. These findings are consistent with prior work by Rotino et al. (2005), who reported significant inter-varietal variation in carotenoid content. Similarly, lycopene content ranged from 3.02 mg/100 g to 31.629 mg/100 g. Lycopene

is a potent antioxidant linked to reduced risks of cardiovascular diseases and certain cancers (Tufail et al., 2024). The high lycopene levels observed in some of the tomato varieties highlight their potential as nutraceutical-rich varieties for both fresh consumption and processing into functional foods. These results corroborate the findings of Fadupin et al. (2024), who reported lycopene values of 5.73–30.50 mg/100 g among tomato varieties, emphasizing the variability in antioxidant potential in tomatoes. The DNA quality assessment revealed A260/A280 ratios ranging from 1.457 to 2.000. This aligns with the findings of Waghmare et al. (2023) and Abdel-Latif and Osman (2017), who reported similar DNA quality ranges in tomato. Varieties with lower purity ratios, are likely to contain protein or phenolic contaminants that could interfere with PCR or sequencing. These results imply that while the CTAB extraction protocol is effective, some varieties may require additional purification steps to yield DNA suitable for high molecular analyses.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from this study that the tomato varieties with a lower level of moisture content, will have a longer shelf life and reduced susceptibility to microbial spoilage, making them suitable for processing and storage. NGB02691(V2), NGB02695(V3), NGB00697(V9), NGB00707(V10), and Platinum701F1 (V27) are very high in beta-carotene capable of contributing to the prevention of vitamin A deficiency and associated health disorders. While NGB00749 (V24), Diva F1(V26), and NGB00746 (V23) are also very high in lycopene indicating that they possess high antioxidant potential, which can help mitigate oxidative stress and reduce the risk of cardiovascular diseases and cancer. Hence, these varieties can be recommended for production on a large scale in order to mitigate the problems associated with Vitamin A deficiency, cardiovascular-diseases and any other chronic illnesses. The study also revealed that the use of the CTAB DNA extraction protocol is very efficient in tomato.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledged the Head, tomato germplasm centre of the National Centre for Genetic Resources and Biotechnology (NACGRAB), Ibadan, Oyo - State, Nigeria; for the supply of the tomato varieties utilized for the research. The contribution of Mrs C.O. Adeniran, Department of Animal Production and Health, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria for the beta-carotene and lycopene content analysis is also acknowledged.

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